

AUTOMATED FEEDING SYSTEM

1. Automated feeding system for Celtic pigs in forest areas of Galicia (NW Spain) 2. Celtic pigs feeding in the automated feeding system. 3. & 4. Installations of the automated feeding system.

THE WHAT AND WHY:

Forest fires are one of the most significant environmental challenges in northern Spain and Portugal. In these regions, the high risk of forest fires is mainly due to the accumulation of biomass in the understorey, which can be reduced through the implementation of silvopastoral systems with autochthonous breeds such as the Celtic pig. This agroforestry practice not only decreases the biomass load in the understorey but also produces a high-quality product, while promoting animal welfare and enhancing land use efficiency. However, when Celtic pigs are used to implement silvopastoral systems it is important to incorporate new technologies to manage grazing activities effectively. In this context, an autonomous and digitalised feeding system was developed under the Forestcelta operational group to ensure proper control and monitoring of the animals.

Keywords: Forest fires, biomass, autochthonous breeds, Celtic pig, animal welfare, digitalisation, Pavlov reflex

HOW IS THE CHALLENGE ADDRESSED

How to develop an autonomous and digitalised feeding system?

The autonomous and digitalised feeding system is a modular system composed of mobile panels that can be moved throughout the forest area, allowing the stocking rate to be adjusted based on biomass accumulation in the understorey. This system is based on the Pavlovian reflex mechanism, in which animals learn to associate a specific sound with food delivery. The sound is emitted daily at the same time, enabling the farmer to gather the animals for monitoring using solar-powered cameras. In addition, this feeding system enables the farmer to track the amount of food provided to the animals at any given time, which is adjusted as the animals grow. Animals are introduced to the autonomous and digitalized feeding system between 2 and 4 months of age and are slaughtered at 14 to 15 months.

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ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

The development of this autonomous and digitalised feeding system has shown that there are farmers and forest landowners interested in implementing it on their farms, mainly due to its multiple advantages in comparison with traditional systems. The main advantages are: i) The biomass accumulation in the understorey is reduced, thus decreasing the risk of forest fires sustainably throughout the forest area when the stocking rate is adequate, ii) Production costs are reduced, ii) Income diversification on farms, iv) The management, conservation, and maintenance of autochthonous breeds are facilitated, v) High-quality products are produced and introduced into distribution and consumption channels, vi) The use of digitalization systems facilitates the work of farmers and forest landowners, vii) Population retention in rural areas.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- **The autonomous and digitalised feeding system facilitates the work of farmers and forest landowners**
- **An adequate stocking rate is crucial for reducing the accumulation of flammable biomass in the understorey while maintaining biodiversity and soil health.**
- **The autonomous and digitalised feeding system promotes the production of high-quality products from autochthonous breeds**

Automated feeding system for Celtic pigs in forest areas of Galicia (NW Spain)

Celtic pigs feeding in the forest area

More information online: <https://forescelta.com/>

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